

Lab Protocol

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Attributions

The writing and organization of the Lab Protocols were carried out collectively by *Angeliki Iordanidou, Errika Sylai, and Margarita Papastergiou* under the supervision of *Dr. Stefania Maniatsi, Dr Konstantina Psatha, and Prof. Michalis Aivaliotis*. All members contributed to recording experiments, documenting protocols, and ensuring a complete and accurate representation of our laboratory protocols.

A. Identification and Evaluation of siRNAs Targeting BCL-2 in CLL cells

1. Objective

The purpose of this protocol is to define a systematic approach for identifying and evaluating literature-based small interfering RNAs (siRNAs) targeting the BCL-2 gene in Chronic Lymphocytic Leukemia (CLL) and the MEC-1 cell line. This workflow serves as the foundation for any in silico computational simulations and further therapeutic development.

2. Materials and Resources

- Access to bibliographic databases (PubMed, Scopus, Google Scholar)
- Spreadsheet software (Microsoft Excel, Google Sheets)
- Reference management tools (Mendeley)

3. Methodology

3.1 Literature Review and Data Selection

1. Identify experimentally validated studies involving siRNAs targeting the gene of interest (*e.g., our gene of interest and target: BCL-2 gene*)

A. Keywords:

- “BCL-2 siRNA”
- “Gene silencing”
- “Cancer cell lines”
- “CLL siRNA”
- “BCL-2 inhibition”

*Keywords were used **individually** or in **combination***

B. Search Criteria:

- Inclusion of **experimentally validated** siRNA sequences targeting the gene of interest (**BCL2**)
- Inclusion of siRNA **sequence** (sense and antisense strands)
- Inclusion of transcript variants
- **No restriction** to a specific cancer type, but

1. **Priority 1: Studies involving Chronic Lymphocytic Leukemia (CLL)**

2. **Priority 2: Studies using the MEC-1 cell line (CLL model)**

- Inclusion of **functional and cellular evaluations** (functional assays performed such as viability, apoptosis, etc.)
- Inclusion of **Silencing efficiency** (mRNA and/or protein level reduction)
- **Inclusion of Transfection conditions** (reagent, siRNA concentration, incubation time)
- Inclusion of **off-target assessment** data when available

3.2 Data Extraction and Organization

For each relevant study or dataset, specific information was extracted according to predefined criteria. The data extraction process focused on collecting all parameters relevant to siRNA characterization and experimental validation. The extracted data was compiled into an Excel sheet where siRNAs were numerically sorted. That Excel sheet includes:

- siRNA sequence
- Targeted mRNA sequence or position
- Cancer type and/ or specific cancer cell line
- The transfection method used
- Results (% silencing, protein and mRNA levels, cellular effects, etc.)
- References (DOI)
- A general idea or more information provided

- Additional comments or insights derived from information encountered during our review of the publication

3.3 Categorization of siRNAs

1. **Seven color-coded categories** should be developed, each corresponding to one of the following classification groups:
 - **Tested in CLL:** % good to high silencing, either at mRNA or protein level, good functional effect, limited off targets
 - **Tested in another cell line:** % good to high silencing, either at the mRNA or protein level, good functional effect, limited off-targets
 - **Tested in CLL or not:** % low silencing, poor functional effect, observed off-targets
 - **Tested in CLL based on bioinformatic prediction / in silico screen**
 - **Useful as control** (non-targeting, scrambled, irrelevant targets)
 - **Product from companies** (usually lacks detailed data) / patent
 - **Little data available for siRNA effects in the literature** (papers)
2. Support documentation by classification and comparison of the reported information derived from literature research based on predefined above must be documented.
3. Note as comment in cases where such data were incomplete or missing, relevant contextual details (e.g., siRNA design strategy, transfection method, or notable experimental observation).

3.4 Candidate Prioritization

1. Rank **into three tiers** based on prior categorization for further investigation and annotation. The annotation order is,
 - **High-priority candidates:** Validated in MEC-1/CLL or other cell lines with strong functional data and promising predictions
 - **Medium-priority candidates:** Validated in other cell lines, but with a lack of some data or not so promising predictions or functional data in comparison to the other ones

- **Low-priority candidates:** Incomplete, ineffective, or poorly reported data

Each ranking should be accompanied by a short justification based on our criticism.

3.5 Compilation of BCL2 Technical Sheet: Before Dry Lab

Gathering relevant biological and structural data on the gene of interest and useful notes for use in siRNA design and modeling. The technical sheet followed the previously numbered siRNA entries and summarized key dry-lab primer data.

1. Organize excel sheet to include data about:
 - Structural characteristics of each siRNA
 - Retrieve mRNA and protein sequences from databases (e.g., NCBI)
 - Providing data for the functional domains targeted
 - Designing siRNA data & Information
 - Regions for accessibility and conservation
2. Prioritize and compile the technical sheet establishing a solid bridge for the organized, fully annotated, and explained data ready for silico screening, downstream analysis, and further categorization to select the best candidates out of it.

That protocol is scalable and modular, allowing it to be applied uniformly across all gene targets, ensuring consistent candidate prioritization, data annotation, and technical sheet compilation while enabling adaptation for additional targets such as BTK, STAT3, and beyond.

B. In silico analysis and evaluation of primers for BCL-2 and BTK genes

1. Objective

The purpose of this protocol is to establish a structured workflow for the *in-silico* evaluation of qRT-PCR primer pairs targeting the BCL2 and BTK genes. The analysis focuses on primers retrieved from reviewed literature, emphasizing their relevance in the context of in Chronic Lymphocytic Leukemia (CLL) and the MEC-1 cell line. This protocol includes the verification of primer specificity, secondary structure prediction, and other primer characteristics. It serves as a critical preliminary step before experimental validation and is intended to ensure accuracy in downstream gene expression quantification.

2. Materials and Resources

- Access to bibliographic databases (PubMed, Scopus, Google Scholar, Harvard University Primer Bank)
- Spreadsheet software (Microsoft Excel, Google Sheets)
- Reference management tools (Mendeley)
- Oligoanalyzer™ Tool (by IDT)

3. Methodology

3.1 Literature Review

1. Conduct a comprehensive literature review using relevant keywords and phrases to identify suitable primers for qRT-PCR analysis of *BCL2* and *BTK*.

A. Keywords:

- “BCL-2 primers”
- “BTK primers”
- “ BCL2 qRT-PCR CLL ”
- “ BTK siRNA qPCR ”

*Keywords were used **individually** or in **combination**.*

2. Apply uniformly for all genes of interest
3. Identify and include experimentally validated primer sequences with proven efficacy in literature
4. Prioritize studies involving the disease of interest (e.g. CLL) and consistent with the project's disease cell line model
5. Include validated qRT-PCR primer sequences targeting genes of interest
6. Gather and annotate experimental validated results
7. Prefer studies providing methodological transparency and quantitative performance data

3.2 Data Extraction and Organization

For each primer pair used in conventional PCR or qRT-PCR, relevant information was systematically compiled and organized in a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet to facilitate evaluation and comparison. The spreadsheet included the following fields for each primer set:

1. **Primer Sequences:** Forward and reverse sequences.
2. **GC Content (%):** Percentage of guanine and cytosine bases.
3. **Melting Temperature (T_m):** Calculated melting temperature for each primer.
4. **Self-Dimerization Potential:** ΔG values and number of base pair interactions indicative of potential self-dimers.
5. **Hairpin Formation:** Number of predicted hairpin structures along with their respective ΔG values.
6. **Target Gene/Transcript:** The specific gene or transcript the primer targets (amplification)
7. **Expected PCR Product Size:** In base pairs, when available from source references.
8. **Reference:** Citation (source) from which the primer sequence was obtained.
9. **Literature Usage:** Number of publications using the primer, as identified via Google Scholar.

3.3 Categorization of primer sequences

1. **Implement a color-coded classification system** with each color corresponding to one of the defined evaluation categories.

- **Validated in CLL:** Experimentally tested in CLL cells with high amplification efficiency, target specificity, and great structural features derived from upstream analysis
- **Validated in other human systems:** Experimentally tested in non-CLL human cells with good performance but not confirmed in CLL.
- **Poor performance report:** Shows low efficiency, non-specific amplification, or primer-dimer formation in published or in-house data.
- **Reference gene primer:** Targets standard housekeeping genes commonly used for normalization in CLL or in closely related cell lines experiments

2. Support the classification framework by systematically recording key information for each primer set, including type of biological sample or cell line used for validation, specificity of amplification (e.g., presence of non-specific products or primer-dimer formation), and any indications of technical limitations.

3.4 Candidate Prioritization

1. Rank primer set into three priority tiers for further consideration and use based on the classification criteria described above.

- **High-priority candidates**: Primers experimentally validated in CLL or relevant human cell lines, demonstrating high amplification efficiency, strong specificity and consistent performance across studies.
- **Medium-priority candidates**: Primers tested in other biological systems with generally acceptable performance, but with certain limitations, such as incomplete validation, moderate amplification efficiency, or limited supporting data, when compared to top-tier candidates.
- **Low-priority candidates**: Primers associated with insufficient, inconsistent, or poorly reported data, including lack of validation, low specificity, technical issues (e.g., primer-dimers), or minimal presence in literature.

C. Cell thawing of MEC-1 cells

The thawing of frozen cells is a critical step to re-establishing viable cultures for experimental use. In this process, cryopreserved MEC-1 cells¹ are rapidly thawed from -80°C to minimize ice crystal formation and reduce the cytotoxic effects of dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), a cryoprotectant used during freezing. The following protocol outlines the steps for thawing, centrifuging, and resuspending MEC-1 cells¹ to initiate a healthy culture.

1. Materials

A. Reagents

- RPMI + 20% FBS +1% Pen/strep

*RPMI 1640 supplemented with 20% FBS and 1% pen/strep is used to support optimal growth and stress tolerance of sensitive suspension B-cell lines like MEC-1. A 20% **FBS supplement** provides additional growth factors, hormones, and attachment proteins to ensure cells proliferate after thawing*

B. Equipment

- 1 cryovial of MEC-1 cells (4 million cells)
- Cell culture flask (T-25)
- Inverted Microscope
- Conical falcon tubes (15 -30 mL)
- Centrifuge
- Pipette controller
- Serological pipettes (5 mL, 10 mL)

2. Procedure

- Allow complete medium (RPMI, 20% FBS, 1% pen/strep) to equilibrate at RT before use.
- Transfer a cryovial of MEC-1 cells from -80°C refrigerator directly to the biosafety cabinet.
- Thaw the cryovial at RT gently and rapidly warm it between the palms of the hands until only a small ice crystal remains

- As the vial begins to thaw, withdraw the liquefied portion with a sterile stripette and transfer it into a 15 mL conical falcon tube pre-filled with RT complete medium.
- Perform gentle up-and-down pipetting to ensure mixing.
- Continue this process until the entire contents of the cryovial are thawed and transferred into the conical falcon tube. *The goal is to reduce the DMSO concentration from cytotoxic (10%) to non-toxic (1%).*
- Keep a small aliquot of the cell suspension (~10 μ L) and perform microscopic observation of the cells using a hemocytometer (Neubauer chamber), for accurate counting of their number per culture.
- Centrifuge at 1200 RPM (\approx 300 g) for 5 minutes at RT
- Discard the supernatant.
- Resuspend the cell pellet with the addition of fresh culture medium according to the cell count.
- Transfer the cell mixture to a sterile cell culture flask.
- Place the flask in a 37 °C, 5% CO₂ incubator.

D. Passaging MEC-1 cells

Subculturing cells is a routine procedure that ensures their continued growth and viability over multiple passages. As cells proliferate, they reach high densities that can compromise nutrient availability and alter their physiological state. To maintain optimal growth conditions, cells must be periodically harvested, diluted, and transferred into fresh culture medium. This process not only sustains the cell line but also ensures reproducibility in downstream experiments by keeping the cells in a healthy and exponential growth phase.

1. Materials

A. Reagents

- RPMI +20% FBS + 1% pen/strep
- RPMI + 10% FBS +1% pen/strep

*RPMI 1640 supplemented with 10% FBS and 1% pen/strep provides standard nutrient and growth factor levels suitable for maintaining healthy proliferation of most lymphoid cell lines like MEC-1. **10% FBS provides sufficient growth factors, hormones, and proteins to support normal cell growth and viability while minimizing serum-related variability and cost, making it the standard concentration for routine culture.***

- Trypan Blue

B. Equipment

- Inverted Microscope
- Conical falcon tubes (15-50 mL)
- Centrifuge
- Pipette controller
- Serological pipettes (5 mL, 10 mL)
- Eppendorf
- Micropipettes
- Sterile pipette tips (10 µL)

2. Procedure

- Allow complete medium (RPMI, 20% FBS, 1% pen/strep or RPMI, 10% FBS, 1% pen/strep, while usage of either medium depends on the cell viability and cell proliferation capacity, to equilibrate at room temperature (RT) before use
- Transfer the cell culture flask from the incubator to the microscope and observe cell morphology.
- Transfer the cell culture flask into the biosafety cabinet.
- Collect the cells from the cell culture flask, after performing up and down thoroughly.
- Keep a small aliquot of the cell suspension ($\sim 10 \mu\text{L}$) for the measurement of viable cells using a Neubauer hemocytometer and trypan blue, under the microscope.
- Transfer the cell suspension into a 15 mL conical falcon tube.
- Centrifuge at 1200 RPM ($\approx 300 \text{ g}$) for 5 minutes at RT
- Discard the supernatant
- Resuspend the cell pellet with an appropriate volume of fresh medium so that 1 mL of culture corresponds to $\sim 5 \times 10^5$ cells, which is the optimal cell number for MEC-1 cell line
- Transfer the cells into the cell culture flask
- Handle the cell suspension carefully, ensuring that no liquid remains on the inner side of the flask cap
- Return the cell culture flask to the incubator ($37 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, 5% CO_2)

E. Treatment of MEC1 cells with the GSK126 inhibitor of the EZH2 protein

GSK126 is a selective inhibitor of EZH2 (Enhancer of Zeste Homolog 2), the catalytic subunit of the Polycomb Repressive Complex 2 (PRC2), which catalyzes the trimethylation of histone H3 at lysine 27 (H3K27me3), an epigenetic modification associated with transcriptional repression.^{2,3} In our work, we used GSK126 before siRNA experiments in MEC-1 cells, not only to examine how our model responds to a well-characterized epigenetic inhibitor, but also to assess and establish a control step for dose-dependent cytostatic or cytotoxic effect compared to siRNA experiments.

1. Materials

A. Reagents

- RPMI + 10% FBS+1%Pen/strep
- Trypan Blue (for cell staining)
- DMSO (10 μ L aliquot)
- GSK126 – Solvent DMSO (40 μ L)

B. Equipment

- Inverted Microscope
- Conical falcon tubes (15-30 mL)
- Centrifuge
- Pipette controller
- Micropipettes
- Sterile pipette tips (10,200,1000 μ L)
- Serological pipettes (5 mL, 10 mL)
- Sterile 24-well plate x 2
- 96-well plate
- Neubauer plate (for cell counting)
- Eppendorfs

2. Procedure

1. Observe cell culture flask under the microscope (assess cell morphology, cell aggregates, etc.)
2. Cell homogenization by gently pipetting up and down (in sterile conditions, inside the biosafety cabinet).
3. Take a small volume of cell into a 1,5mL eppendorf
4. Determine cell number and viability (cell number sufficient and viability%>90)
5. Transfer the desired calculated volume of the cell suspension (corresponding to the required optimal number of MEC-1 cells) into a 15 mL sterile conical falcon tube using a pipette controller.
6. Centrifuge the cell suspension at 1200 RPM for 5 minutes at RT
7. While the cells are centrifuging, label the lid of the 24-well plate with the tested conditions and technical replicates for easy reference and preparation the number of conical falcon tubes needed for the different conditions.
8. After centrifugation, carefully discard the supernatant and resuspend the cell pellet in the appropriate calculated volume of culture medium
9. Share V mL of total cell suspension to each conical falcon tube, corresponding to respective conditions and different MM
10. Add GSK126 inhibitor or vehicle control (e.g., DMSO) to each Master Mix - falcon tube accordingly. Mix gently by pipetting up and down. Add **Vwell/2** (μL) from each Master Mix into the appropriate wells, proceeding column by column, top to bottom (e.g., **A1** \rightarrow **B1** \rightarrow **C1** \rightarrow **D1**) **handling one condition per time**.
11. After completing the first round, add the second round of **Vwell/2** (μL) **in reverse vertical order (D1 \rightarrow C1 \rightarrow B1 \rightarrow A1)**. Ensure thorough mixing (up and down) before each addition to maintain homogeneity.
12. The previous step (9) is repeated for each different condition separately and relatively quickly
13. Incubate the 24-well plate for 24 & 48 hours at 37 °C, 5% CO₂

2.1 Day 2 - 24h post-transfection

1. Preparing the cells for staining
2. Label the 96-well plate
3. Allocate 3 wells for each condition.
 - A. Well 1 will contain 100 μ L from the 1st 24-hour technical replicate.
 - B. Well 2 will contain 100 μ L from the 2nd 24-hour technical replicate.
 - C. Well 3 will contain a mix of 50 μ L from each replicate, totaling 100 μ L.
4. Clearly label the lid and sides of the plate to identify each condition.
5. Remove the 24-well plate from the incubator.
6. Observe the cells under the microscope.
7. Place the 24-well plate into the biosafety cabinet.
8. Orient the plate for ease of access.
9. Transfer cell supernatant to the 96-well plate.
10. Gently mix each well (pipette up and down).
11. Transfer the appropriate volume to each designated well in the 96-well plate.
12. Repeat the process 3 times per condition (as described in step 1).
13. Return the 24-well plate to the incubator.
14. Prepare Trypan Blue mixtures
15. Load the Neubauer chamber
16. Transfer 10 μ L of the Trypan Blue–cell mixture into the counting chamber and take 3 measurements per condition
17. Calculate cell viability and growth after each count

2.2 Day 3 - 48h post-transfection

1. Preparing the cells for staining
2. Label the 96-well plate
3. Allocate 3 wells for each condition.
 - A. Well 1 will contain 100 μ L from the 1st 24-hour technical replicate.
 - B. Well 2 will contain 100 μ L from the 2nd 24-hour technical replicate.
 - C. Well 3 will contain a mix of 50 μ L from each replicate, totaling 100 μ L.
4. Clearly label the lid and sides of the plate to identify each condition.
5. Remove the 24-well plate from the incubator.
6. Observe the cells under the microscope.

7. Place the 24-well plate into the biosafety cabinet.
8. Orient the plate for ease of access.
9. Transfer cell supernatant to the 96-well plate.
10. Gently mix each well (pipette up and down).
11. Transfer the appropriate volume to each designated well in the 96-well plate.
12. Repeat the process 3 times per condition (as described in step 1).
13. Return the 24-well plate to the incubator.
14. Prepare Trypan Blue mixtures
15. Load the Neubauer chamber
16. Transfer 10 μL of the Trypan Blue–cell mixture into the counting chamber and take 3 measurements per condition
17. Calculate cell viability and growth after each count

F. siRNA Transfection Protocol

Small interfering RNAs (siRNAs) are short double-stranded RNA molecules that mediate post-transcriptional gene silencing through sequence-specific degradation of target mRNAs. This mechanism allows selective suppression of protein expression by preventing translation of the corresponding mRNA.

1. Materials

A. Reagents

- RPMI + 10% FBS + 1% Pen/strep
- RPMI + 10% FBS
- Trypan Blue (for cell staining)
- siRNA aliquots
- INTERFERin reagent (INTERFERin®)
- Opti-MEM
- Milli-Q water

B. Equipment

- Inverted Microscope
- Conical falcon tubes (15-50 mL)
- Centrifuge
- Pipette controller
- Micropipettes
- Sterile pipette tips (10, 200, 1000 μ L)
- Serological pipettes (5 mL, 10 mL)
- Sterile 24-well plates
- 96-well plate
- Conical falcon tubes (15mL)
- Neubauer plate (for cell counting)
- Eppendorf tubes
- GloMax®-Multi+ Detection System
- Black 96-well plate for fluorescence

2. Procedure

2.1 Preliminary siRNAs' preparation and cell calculations - Day 0

1. Dilution of siRNA stocks

- Dilute each siRNA stock by mixing with siRNA dissolving buffer and 1× siMAX Universal Buffer according to the manufacturer's recommendations.

2. Resuspension

- Vortex each tube gently for 5 seconds.
- Briefly centrifuge to collect contents at the bottom.
- Incubate at RT for 10 minutes to ensure complete solubilization.

3. Aliquoting (general siRNA stocks)

- Prepare aliquots of siRNA at the designated working concentration (5 pmol/μL).
- Store aliquots at -20 °C until use.

4. Cell seeding Set up (cell calculations)

Table 1: Recommended number of suspension cells to seed the day of transfection.

Culture Vessel	Number of suspension cells to seed the day of transfection	Volume of medium per well
384 -well	5. 000 – 10.000	25 μL
96-well	10.000 – 20.000	50 μL
48-well	100.000 – 200.000	200 μL
24-well	200.000 – 400.000	500 μL
6-well	500.000 - 2 x 10 ⁶	1 mL
6 cm / flask 25 cm ²	2x 10 ⁶ - 5 x 10 ⁶	2 mL

** Adjust volumes and concentrations per the manufacturer's protocol and your cell line's behavior, beginning with the suggested ranges and optimizing in a small pilot. INTERFERin® in vitro siRNA/miRNA transfection reagent PROTOCOL*

Table 2. Recommended volumes of INTERFERin® according to the siRNA concentration and the plate format for transfection of cells grown in suspension.

Final siRNA concentration	Plate format	Volume INTERFERin® reagent/well
1 to 20 nM	6-well or 35 mm	10+8ul
1 to 20 nM	24-well	3 ± 2 µL
20 to 50 nM	6-well or 35 mm	15 ± 8 µL
20 to 50 nM	24-well	5 ± 2 µL

***Adjust volumes per manufacturer's protocol and your cell line's behavior, siRNAs concentrations beginning with the suggested ranges and optimizing in a small pilot. INTERFERin® in vitro siRNA/miRNA transfection reagent PROTOCOL*

2.2 siRNA Transfection - Day 1

1. Cell Observation and Counting

- Observe cells under the inverted microscope and capture representative images
- Withdraw a small aliquot of cell suspension for viability assessment
- Return the culture flask to the incubator
- Assess cell viability using Trypan Blue exclusion
- Determine viable cell concentration with a hemocytometer, (% viability >90%, sufficient cell number for downstream experiment based on conditions and cell seeding set -up)

2. Plate Preparation

- Calculate the required cell suspension volume based on the experimental design (Table 1)

- Label plates clearly according to post-transfection day and experimental condition
- Place labeled plates inside the biosafety cabinet

3. Preparation of Master Mixes

- In a sterile labeled RNase-free Eppendorf tube, add the appropriate volume of Opti-MEM, adjusted according to the number of cells to be treated and Master Mix calculations
- Add the respective volume of siRNA solution, that was stored in $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, to the tube
- Vortex INTERFERin® reagent for 5 sec and spin down before use.
- Add the appropriate volume of INTERFERin reagent to each master mix tube in sequence (Table 2)
- Mix immediately for 10 seconds using vortex.
- Incubate for 15 minutes at RT to allow INTERFERin®/siRNA complexes to form (do not exceed 30 min).

Note: Ensure that Growth Mediums, Opti-MEM, INTERFERin, and siRNA solutions are equilibrated to RT before use.

4. Cell Seeding

- During the incubation period, and while waiting for the required time to elapse, begin preparing and performing the cell seeding process to ensure workflow efficiency and readiness for subsequent experimental steps
- Transfer the required volume of cell suspension into a conical falcon tube
- Centrifuge at 1200 RPM for 5min at RT
- Discard the supernatant
- Resuspend the cell pellet in the calculated final volume of medium without antibiotics
- Seed cells into well - plates by dispensing equal volumes (200 μl /well)

5. Transfection

- Dispense the complexes into the plate's wells according to the respective experimental condition, ensuring equal distribution across replicates
- Add the 100 μL INTERFERin®/siRNA /Opti-MEM mix per well into the 200 μL of cells suspension in growth medium
- Gently swirl the plate to ensure homogeneous distribution
- Place the plates in the incubator at 37 °C with 5% CO₂

6. Medium Supplementation

- After 4h-6h incubation, add complete growth medium with antibiotics containing serum and antibiotics to each well
- Return plates to the incubator and maintain under standard culture conditions

2.3 6 hours Post-Transfection- Day1

1. Retrieve the 6-h plate from the incubator
2. Observe cells across all conditions under microscope for morphological assessment and capture representative images
3. Do medium Supplementation (step 6), after 4h-6h incubation, add complete growth medium with antibiotics containing serum and antibiotics to each well
4. Collect cell suspension for assessment of transfection success:
 - a. Transfer a small volume (1/3 of well volume) to a conical falcon tube accounting for ≥ 100.000 cells
 - b. Centrifuge at 2000 RPM for 10 minutes at 4°C
 - c. Discard supernatant
 - d. Wash with sterilled PBS (500 μl /sample)
 - e. Centrifuge at 2000 RPM for 10 minutes at 4°C
 - f. Discard supernatant

- g. Resolution in 60 μ l sterilled PBS for each sample
5. Vortex and spin down samples
6. Load 50 μ l of each condition in 96-well- black fluorescence plate
7. Set up program in GloMax®-Multi+ Detection System with Instinct® Software
8. Detect possible signal and evaluate siRNA fluorescence data
9. Record all data. No additional procedures are performed on this day.

Note: Minimize light exposure for optimal detection

2.4 24 hours Post-Transfection - Day 2

1. Retrieve the 24-h plate from the incubator
2. Observe cells across all conditions under microscope for morphological assessment and capture representative images
3. Collect cell suspension for assessment of transfection success:
 - a. Transfer a small volume (1/3 of well volume) to a conical falcon tube accounting for ≥ 100.000 cells
 - b. Centrifuge at 2000 RPM for 10 minutes at 4°C
 - c. Discard supernatant
 - d. Wash Step with sterilled PBS (500 μ l/sample)
 - e. Centrifuge at 2000 RPM for 10 minutes at 4°C
 - f. Discard supernatant
 - g. Resolution in 60 μ l sterilled PBS for each sample
4. Vortex and spin down samples
5. Load 50 μ l of each condition in 96-well- black fluorescence plate
6. Set up program in GloMax®-Multi+ Detection System with Instinct® Software
7. Detect possible signal and evaluate siRNA fluorescence data
8. Collect 10-20 μ l cell suspension per condition for assessment of cell viability & growth
9. Perform cell counting and viability analysis using Trypan Blue.

10. The rest of the cell suspension volume (2/3 per well) is stored appropriately for use during RNA extraction
11. Prepare an additional plate under identical conditions to be harvested for protein extraction (Set up a duplicate plate with the same seeding and treatment conditions for protein extraction) and do pellets for downstream experiments
12. Record all data. No additional procedures are performed on this day.

Note: Minimize light exposure for optimal detection

2.5 48 hours Post-Transfection - Day 3

1. Retrieve the 48-h plate from the incubator
2. Observe cells across all conditions under microscope for morphological assessment and capture representative images
3. Collect cell suspension for assessment of transfection success:
 - a. Transfer a small volume (1/3 of well volume) to a conical falcon tube accounting for $\geq 100,000$ cells
 - b. Centrifuge at 2000 RPM for 10 minutes at 4°C
 - c. Discard supernatant
 - d. Wash Step with sterilled PBS (500 ul/sample)
 - e. Centrifuge at 2000 RPM for 10 minutes at 4°C
 - f. Discard supernatant
 - g. Resuspension in 60 μ l sterilled PBS for each sample
4. Vortex and spin down samples
5. Load 50 μ l of each condition in 96-well- black fluorescence plate
6. Set up program in GloMax®-Multi+ Detection System with Instinct® Software
7. Detect possible signal and evaluate siRNA fluorescence data
8. Collect 10-20 μ l cell suspension per condition for assessment of cell viability & growth
9. Perform cell counting and viability analysis using Trypan Blue.

10. The rest of the cell suspension volume (2/3 per well) is stored appropriately for use during RNA extraction
11. Prepare an additional plate under identical conditions to be harvested for protein extraction (Set up a duplicate plate with the same seeding and treatment conditions for protein extraction) and do pellets for downstream experiments
12. Record all data. No additional procedures are performed on this day.

Note: Based on your experimental design you might not proceed with further steps. If not performing Step F and G

Note: Minimize light exposure for optimal detection

2.6 72 hours Post-Transfection - Day 4

1. Retrieve the 72-h plate from the incubator
2. Observe cells across all conditions under microscope for morphological assessment and capture representative images
3. Perform cell counting and viability determination using Trypan Blue.
4. Assess total cell number (“stock”) for suitability of molecular extraction.
5. Do pellets and store harvested material at appropriate conditions (e.g., -20 °C).

2.7 96 Hours Post-Transfection - Day 5

1. Retrieve the 72-h plate from the incubator
2. Observe cells across all conditions under microscope for morphological assessment and capture representative images
3. Perform cell counting and viability determination using Trypan Blue.
4. Assess total cell number (“stock”) for suitability of molecular extraction.
5. Do pellets and store harvested material at appropriate conditions (e.g., -20 °C).

G. INTERFERin titration in MEC-1 cells for cytotoxicity investigation

The following protocol outlines the steps for testing varying volumes of INTERFERin to establish the optimal working concentration for downstream experiments. Before proceeding with the experiment, it is essential to ensure that enough MEC-1 cells are available. This requires initiating cell culture in advance, following the standard procedures for cell thawing and reculturing to expand the population to the necessary density for the planned conditions.

1. Materials

A. Reagents

- Trypan Blue
- INTERFERin® Transfection reagent
- Opti-MEM (serum-free medium)

B. Equipment

- Neubauer hemocytometer
- Inverted microscope
- Conical falcon tubes: (15 and 30 mL)
- Sterile 24-well plates
- 96-well plate
- Pipette controller
- Micropipettes
- Sterile pipette tips (10,200, 1000 μ L)
- Serological pipettes (5 mL, 10 mL)
- Vortex mixer

2. Procedure

2.1 Transfection - Day 0

1. Cell Observation

- Place the cell culture flask under the inverted microscope
- Check cell morphology, confluency, and confirm absence of contamination

2. Cell Counting and Viability

- Withdraw 10 μ L of the cell suspension
- Mix with an equal volume of Trypan Blue
- Perform cell counting using a hemocytometer
- Apply Quality thresholds:
 - a. Viability $\geq 90\%$
 - b. Cell density is sufficient for the planned experimental layout
 - c. Continue only if the required number of cells is available ($\geq 5.5 \times 10^6$ cells)

Note: Retain extra cells for possible re-seeding or backup cultures

3. Preparation for Master Mixes

- Label five 15 mL conical falcon tubes with the name of each Master Mix (MM)
- Prepare two 24-well plates, labeling wells according to experimental conditions
- Add the calculated volume of 600 μ l of Opti-MEM into each conical falcon tube (based on the experimental setup and well number)
- Vortex INTERFERin® reagent for 5 seconds and spin down briefly before use
- Add the pre-calculated volume of INTERFERin® to each conical falcon tube (per Master Mix, calculated for 4 replicates)

- Use a new sterile pipette tip for each addition
- Mix immediately by vortexing for ~10 seconds
- Incubate the mixtures at RT for 15 minutes to allow complex formation.
Do not exceed 30 minutes

4. Cell Seeding

- During the 15-minute incubation of the complexes:
- Collect the required volume of the cell suspension from the culture flask
- Divide the suspension into two conical falcon tubes corresponding to the two-seeding setup
- Centrifuge briefly, discard the supernatant, and resuspend the cell pellet in 2.2 mL of fresh medium.
- Plate the cells by dispensing 200 μ L per well into the 24-well plates

5. Addition of Master Mixes

- After the 15-minute incubation:
- Add the corresponding volume of each Master Mix into the appropriate wells by mirroring
- Gently rock or tap the plate to ensure even distribution of complexes
- Place the plates in the incubator at 37 °C, 5% CO₂

6. Medium supplementation

- At 5 hours post-INTERFERin exposure, add 700 μ L of complete medium to each well under all conditions to bring the final volume up to 1 mL
- Use a fresh pipette tip for each well to avoid cross-contamination

Table 3. Transfection setup in MEC-1 cells with INTERFERin -only

Condition	Volume of medium w/o serum for complexation (μL)	Volume of INTERFERin [®] reagent (μL)/well	MM Volume of medium w/o serum for complexation (μL)	MM volume INTERFERin [®] reagent (μL)/well	total MM	(μL)/well
control	100	0	600	0	600	100
1μL	100	1	600	6	606	101
2μL	100	2	600	12	612	102
3μL	100	3	600	18	618	103
5μL	100	5	600	30	630	105

**Calculated for 6 conditions (4wells+½*4wells) for pipetting errors, Master Mix (MM)*

2.2 Day 1 - 24h post-transfection

- Retrieve the 24-h plate from the incubator
- Examine all wells microscopically for morphological assessment and capture representative images.
- Perform cell counting and viability determination using the Trypan Blue exclusion assay.
- Record all data. **No additional procedures are performed on this day.**

2.3 Day 2 - 48h post-transfection

- Retrieve the 48-h plate from the incubator
- Examine all wells microscopically for morphological assessment and capture representative images.
- Perform cell counting and viability determination using the Trypan Blue exclusion assay.
- Record all data. **No additional procedures are performed on this day.**

H. Total RNA extraction in MEC-1 cells

The extraction of RNA from cells is a fundamental procedure that enables the study of gene expression and molecular pathways. Since RNA is highly susceptible to degradation by endogenous RNases, the process must be carried out carefully under controlled conditions to preserve sample integrity. The following protocol, based on the **Monarch® Spin RNA Isolation Kit (Mini)**, outlines the steps for harvesting cells and extracting total RNA to ensure purity, integrity, and reproducibility of results.

1. Materials

A. Reagents

- DNase I
- Mec-1 cell pellets
- Proteinase K
- $\geq 95\%$ Ethanol
- Nuclease-free Water
- Monarch Buffer BX
- Monarch Buffer WZ
- Monarch StabiLyse DNA/RNA Buffer

B. Equipment

- Centrifuge
- Eppendorf tubes
- Micropipettes
- Sterile pipette tips (10, 200, 1000 μL)
- 1mL insulin needle

2. Procedure

The following preparatory steps were performed a few days prior to the RNA extraction experiment to ensure smooth execution and optimal sample quality.

A. Rehydration of DNase I

1. Place the glass vial containing lyophilized enzyme on the RNase-free benchtop.
2. Unscrew the cap and place the cap upside down on the benchtop.
3. Remove the grey rubber stopper and place it securely inside the inverted screw cap.
4. Using a pipette, dispense appropriate volume of the supplied Nuclease-free Water onto the lyophilized DNase I.

- ***Dispensing 550 μ L Nuclease-free Water***

5. mix 8-10 times adjusting the tip positioning inside the vial such that all the lyophilized material gets hydrated. Do not vortex.
6. Place the vial back on the bench.
7. The solution will turn clear within 15 seconds. Let it stay for an additional minute.
8. The rehydrated DNase I is ready for use in the RNA isolation protocol.
9. Store the rehydrated DNase I at -20°C . Avoid more than 3 freeze-thaw cycles.

B. Aliquoting Proteinase K+

1. Place the glass vial containing lyophilized enzyme on the RNase-free benchtop.
2. Create desired aliquots.
3. Stored at -20°C .
4. Read for use.

C. Preparation of Monarch Buffer BX

1. Add the appropriate volume of the Nuclease-free Water supplied to the reagent bottle.
2. Add the appropriate volume of $\geq 95\%$ ethanol (user-supplied).

3. Ready for use.

D. Preparation of Monarch Buffer WZ

1. Add the appropriate volume of $\geq 95\%$ ethanol (user-supplied).
2. Ready for use.

Part A

1. Determine the volume of Monarch StabiLyse DNA/RNA Buffer needed for your sample according to the table below:

Sample input Amount	Volume of Monarch StabiLyse DNA/RNA Buffer
Tissue (up to 10 mg)	200 μ L
Tissue (10-50 mg)	400 μ L
Leukocytes (up to 1.000.000)	200 μ L
Leukocytes (1.000.000-5.000.000)	400 μ L

2. Add the appropriate volume of Monarch StabiLyse DNA/RNA Buffer to the sample.
3. Add an equal volume of Nuclease-free Water to the sample.
4. Perform sample homogenization using a bead mill or similar device, according to the manufacturer's protocol. If not performing mechanical homogenization, proceed to **Step 8**.
5. *Place the sample tubes on ice for 2 minutes. This step ensures the samples recover from the heat generated during mechanical homogenization.*
6. *Centrifuge at 16,000 x g for 2 minutes. This step helps to pellet debris and minimize the foam generated during mechanical homogenization.*
7. *Transfer the supernatant to a new 1.5 ml RNase-free microfuge tube. It is common for the volume to recover at this step to be slightly less than the input.*
8. For every 350-400 μ l of Monarch StabiLyse DNA/RNA Buffer/Sample mixture, add 15 μ l Proteinase K. Vortex for 5 seconds, and incubate at 55 °C according to the chart below:

Sample type	Incubation time at 55 °C
Homogenized Tissues	5 minutes
Solid tissues (if not performing bead homogenization)	5-30 minutes
Leukocytes	30 minutes

9. Vortex sample for 5 seconds and spin 16,000 x g for 2 minutes to pellet debris. Digested proteins will form a pellet at this stage.
10. Transfer supernatant to an RNase-free microfuge tube
11. Add an equal volume of Monarch StabiLyse DNA/RNA Buffer and vortex for 5 seconds.
12. Proceed to Step 1 of **Part B**: RNA Binding and Elution.

Part B:

1. Transfer up to 700 μ l of the sample from Part I to Monarch Spin Column S2C (orange) fitted in a Monarch Spin Collection Tube. For sample identification, label collection tubes, as columns, will be discarded in the next step.
2. Centrifuge for 1 minute. Discard the column. Save the flow-through in the already existing collection tube.
3. Genomic DNA is captured on the Monarch Spin Column S2C matrix, while **RNA is collected in the flow-through.**
4. To the flow-through, add an equal volume of ethanol ($\geq 95\%$) (user-supplied) and mix thoroughly by pipetting.
5. Do not vortex.
6. Transfer 700 μ l of the sample/ethanol mixture to a Monarch Spin Column S2A (clear) fitted in a new Monarch Spin Collection Tube.
7. Centrifuge for 1 minute. Discard the flow-through. Reload the column with any remaining sample/ethanol mixture, centrifuge and discard the flow-through after each spin.

8. Add 700 μ l Monarch Buffer WZ and centrifuge for 1 minute. Discard the flow-through. This step ensures removal of excess salt, creates conditions optimal for DNase treatment and improves the purity of resulting RNA.
9. **Optional but recommended DNase treatment:** If further gDNA removal is essential for downstream applications, proceed to on-column DNase I treatment, Step 7A–7C. If not, proceed to Step 8.
10. 7A. In an RNase-free microfuge tube (not included), combine 10 μ l Monarch DNase I, Lyophilized with 70 μ l Monarch DNase I Reaction Buffer.
11. 7B. Pipet 80 μ l DNase reaction mixture directly to the top of the matrix.
12. 7C. Incubate for 15 minutes at RT. Proceed to Step 8.
13. Add 500 μ l Monarch Buffer BX and centrifuge for 1 minute. Discard the flow-through. This buffer serves as a priming step.
14. Add 500 μ l Monarch Buffer WZ and centrifuge for 1 minute. Discard the flow-through.
15. Add another 500 μ l Monarch Buffer WZ and centrifuge for 2 minutes. This step ensures removal of residual ethanol.
16. Transfer the column to a 1.5 ml RNase-free microfuge tube (user-supplied). **Use care to ensure the tip of the column does not contact the flow-through.** If in doubt, centrifuge again for 1 minute to ensure no ethanol is carried over.
17. Add 20-100 μ l Nuclease-free Water directly to the center of the column matrix and spin for 30 seconds. For maximal recovery, elute with at least 20 μ l. Elution with 10 μ L is possible, with up to 5-10% loss in recovery.
18. Place eluted RNA on ice if being used for downstream steps, at -20°C for short-term storage (less than 1 week), or at -80°C for long-term storage.

I. RNA measurement of siRNA treated MEC-1 cells.

The quantification of RNA in siRNA-treated MEC-1 cells is a crucial step for evaluating gene silencing efficiency and ensuring the reliability of downstream molecular analyses. Accurate RNA measurement allows the assessment of both RNA integrity and yield, which are essential for obtaining reproducible and meaningful results in quantitative reverse transcription PCR (qRT-PCR). The following protocol describes the procedure for measuring RNA concentration and purity from siRNA-treated MEC-1 samples.

1. Materials

A. Reagents

- Elution Buffer (blank)
- RNA samples

B. Equipment

- NanoDrop spectrophotometer
- Micropipette
- Sterile micropipette tips

2. Procedure

1. Clean pedestals

- Apply 2–3 drops RNase-free water to pedestal close and open, wipe both with a fresh wipe

2. Measure samples

- Pipette 2.0 μL of your elution buffer (blank) the onto the first well of pedestal at the plate
- Pipette 2.0 μL of RNA onto the well of pedestal at the plate, following the blank well. Avoid bubbles and change tips each time (*load 4 samples per 1 measurement repeat the process until all samples are measured*)
- Tap Measure

- Record: concentration (ng/ μ L), A260/A280, A260/A230, and the spectral trace if your software allows saving
- Raise arm and wipe wells and both pedestals
- Repeat for the triplicate aliquot of the same sample. If the triplicate differs by >10%, measure a fourth time

J. cDNA Synthesis

Following whole RNA extraction from treated or non-treated MEC-1 cells, cDNA synthesis represents the essential next step, providing the template required for downstream applications such as RT-qPCR and gene expression analysis.

1. Materials

A. Reagents

- SensiFAST 5× TransAmp™ Buffer (includes priming blend: anchored oligo(dT) + random hexamers)- **BIO-65053**
- DNase/RNase-free water

B. Equipment

- Micropipettes
- 0.5 mL PCR tubes
- Ice bucket
- Thermal cycler with heated lid
- Microcentrifuge for brief spins
- RNase decontaminant (e.g., 70% ethanol)

2. Procedure

Reaction Setup (20 µL per reaction)

Prepare a master mix for N samples plus 10% excess to minimize pipetting error:

Table 4. Reverse Transcription Reaction Setup

Component	Per reaction	Final in 20 μ L
5\times TransAmp Buffer	4.0 μL	1\times
Reverse Transcriptase	1.0 μL	—
RNA (up to 1 μg)	n μL	—
DNase/RNase-free water	to 20 μL	—
Optional: RNase inhibitor	as needed	—

Example master mix for 12 reactions (10 samples + 2 controls) with 10% excess:

- *5 \times TransAmp: $4.0 \mu\text{L} \times 12 \times 1.10 = 52.8 \mu\text{L}$*
- *Reverse Transcriptase: $1.0 \mu\text{L} \times 12 \times 1.10 = 13.2 \mu\text{L}$*
- *Water: calculated as $20 \mu\text{L} - (\text{RNA volume} + 5 \mu\text{L enzymes/buffer})$ per tube*

Thermal Cycling Program

- 25 $^{\circ}$ C – 10 minutes (primer annealing)
- 42 $^{\circ}$ C – 15 minutes (reverse transcription)
- Optional: 48 $^{\circ}$ C – 15 minutes (highly structured RNA)
- 85 $^{\circ}$ C – 5 minutes (enzyme inactivation)
- Hold 4 $^{\circ}$ C (or place on ice)

Step-by-Step

- Thaw kit reagents on ice, mix gently, and spin down briefly. Decontaminate workspace and use RNase-free tips/tubes.
- Prepare mixture on ice. Aliquot master mix into tubes/wells.
- Add the appropriate volume of RNA to each tube. Adjust volume with RNase-free water to 20 μ L total

Wet Lab Team

- Mix by gentle pipetting and spin down briefly.
- Run the thermal cycling program with lid heated (≥ 105 °C).
- Place completed reactions on ice. Proceed to qPCR or store at -20°C .

L. qPCR Protocol

1. Materials

- cDNA template (from reverse-transcribed RNA samples)
- Forward and reverse primers (gene-specific)
- EQ 2× qPCR Master Mix Green, w/o ROX (EnzyQuest, Cat RN014S) (premixed: hot start DNA polymerase, dNTPs, SYBR Green dye, optimized buffer).
- Nuclease-free water
- PCR tubes
- Real-time PCR thermocycler

Table 5. qPCR Reaction Setup for Gene Expression Analysis

Competent	Stock	Volume	Final
EQ 2× qPCR Master Mix Green (w/o ROX)	2×	10.0 μL	1×
Forward primer	10 μM	0.8 μL (range 0.2–1.6)	0.4 μM (0.1–0.8)
Reverse primer	10 μM	0.8 μL (range 0.2–1.6)	0.4 μM (0.1–0.8)
Template DNA/cDNA	—	Y μL	see below
Nuclease-free water	—	to 20.0 μL	

(Scale volumes accordingly if using 25 μL or 10 μL reaction mixtures.)

2. Procedure

1. Preparation for Reaction Mix

- Thaw all reagents on ice.
- Vortex briefly and spin down.
- Prepare a master mix for all samples to minimize pipetting error
- Vortex briefly and spin down.
- Share respective volume of MM solution to each condition properly
- Add cDNA template
- Seal PCR tubes
- Place them at the rotor of Real-time PCR thermocycler

*Prepare a master-mix calculating for “ $1.1 * \text{Number of reactions needed}$ ”. E.g. If 10 reactions are needed, prepare a master mix for $1.1 * 10 = 11$ reactions. Round up to the closest higher integer.*

2. Cycling Program

Table 6. qPCR Thermal Cycling Program *Recommended by Manufacturer*

Step	Cycles	Temperature (°C)	Time	Notes
Polymerase activation	1	95	10-15 min	Hot-start activation. Do not shorten, efficiency drops if reduced.
Denaturation	40	95	10 s	—
Anneal/Extend + Read	40	60	30 s	Acquire fluorescence here. Set exact temp based on primer T_m (optimize by gradient).
Melt	Per cycle	60 to 95	1s	

(typical for amplicons ~80–200 bp)

M. Preparation of Agarose Gel for Electrophoresis

1. Materials

A. Reagents:

- Agarose powder
- Electrophoresis buffer: TBE
- Nucleic acid stain: Ethidium bromide (EtBr)
- Gel Loading Dye, Purple (6X)
- Fast Gene DNA Marker 50 bp
- Nuclease-free water

B. Equipment

- Microwave
- Casting tray, comb(s), gel tank, power supply
- UV & imaging system

C. Guide: Choose Gel%

Table 7. Recommended Agarose Gel Concentrations for DNA Fragment Size Resolution

Target size (bp)	Agarose %
10,000–20,000	0.5%
3,000–10,000	0.8%
1,000–3,000	1.0%
300–1,500	1.5%
100–700	2.0%
50–200	2.5–3.0%

2. Procedure

1. Weigh agarose and add to 1× buffer (TBE) in a heat-proof flask.
2. Melt the agarose/buffer mixture in the microwave (swirl intermittently) until agarose is completely dissolved.
3. Add EtBr to a concentration of 0.5 µg / ml.
4. Pour the gel into the casting tray with combs. Allow to solidify (20–30 minutes).
5. Mix nucleic acid with loading dye (1× final concentration).
6. Load ladder and samples into wells.
7. Run the gel at 100 V until the dye front has migrated 70–80% of the gel length.
8. Visualize under UV and capture an image.

Bibliography:

1. <https://www.dsmz.de/collection/catalogue/details/culture/ACC-497>
2. Park S, Jo SH, Kim JH, Kim SY, Ha JD, Hwang JY, Lee MY, Kang JS, Han TS, Park SG, Kim S, Park BC, Kim JH. Combination Treatment with GSK126 and Pomalidomide Induces B-Cell Differentiation in *EZH2* Gain-of-Function Mutant Diffuse Large B-Cell Lymphoma. *Cancers (Basel)*, 2020 doi: 10.3390/cancers12092541
3. Malik Bissier, Narendra Wajapeyee; Mechanisms of resistance to EZH2 inhibitors in diffuse large B-cell lymphomas. *Blood* 2018; 131 (19): 2125–2137. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1182/blood-2017-08-804344>

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